

Literature Survey on Evaluation of High Volume Fly Ash (HVFA) Concrete Mechanical Properties after Being Exposed to High Temperatures

Onkar Yadav, Ajay Kumar

Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Sandip University, Madhubani, Bihar, India

Mukesh Kumar

Research Scholar, Department of Civil Engineering, Sandip University, Madhubani, Bihar, India

Annotation: The disposal of waste has become a significant global challenge faced by nations worldwide. One such waste material is fly ash, which is produced as a by-product of coal combustion in thermal power plants. With the growing scarcity of raw materials and the urgent need for environmental protection, there is a pressing demand for the development of new building materials that utilize industrial waste, such as fly ash, as a means of sustainable waste management. Pozzolanic concretes, which incorporate fly ash as a key component, are widely used in various industries including oil, gas, nuclear, and power generation due to their advantageous structural properties, environmental sustainability, and energy efficiency. However, these concretes are often exposed to high temperatures for extended periods in these industries, posing a risk of fire and thermal damage. While concrete is generally considered to be fire-resistant, it can experience significant deterioration or even catastrophic failure when subjected to high temperatures. The chemical transformation of the gel within the concrete matrix weakens the bonding, resulting in a loss of strength in fly ash concrete. Therefore, it is crucial to study the mechanical properties of high volume fly ash (HVFA) concrete when exposed to elevated temperatures, particularly up to 120°C. Understanding the behavior of HVFA concrete under thermal conditions is essential for assessing its performance and ensuring its suitability in applications where high temperatures are encountered. By investigating the effects of elevated temperatures on HVFA concrete, researchers aim to improve its resistance to thermal damage and enhance its overall durability, contributing to sustainable waste management and the development of environmentally friendly construction materials.

Key words: Waste disposal, Fly ash, Pozzolanic concretes, Elevated temperatures, Mechanical properties, Sustainable construction materials.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pozzolanic concretes are widely utilized in industries such as oil, gas, nuclear, and power due to their exceptional structural performance, environmental sustainability, and energy-saving benefits. Despite being regarded as a reliable fireproofing material, these concretes face significant challenges when exposed to high temperatures in industrial settings. The chemical transformation of the gel within the concrete matrix weakens the bonding, resulting in a loss of strength and potential damage or failure at elevated temperatures. To address these concerns, extensive research has been conducted on alternative binders and cement replacement materials. Fly ash, volcanic ash, volcanic pumice, pulverized-fuel ash, blast slag, and silica fume have been investigated as potential substitutes for cement. These pozzolanic materials react with lime during cement hydration, improving concrete durability, strength gain rate, and reducing heat liberation,

which is particularly beneficial for mass concrete applications. While the effects of high temperatures on concrete containing fly ash or natural pozzolans have not been extensively studied compared to fly ash concrete, it is evident that concrete properties undergo changes within the range of 100-300°C. Beyond 300°C, there is a decrease in mechanical characteristics. However, the specific impact on concrete strength varies depending on the test conditions and constituent materials used. Further research is needed to comprehensively understand the behavior of pozzolanic concretes under high-temperature conditions and optimize their performance in diverse industrial applications.

2. EFFECT OF FIRE ON CONCRETE

Fire has played a significant role in the development of human civilization, but it also poses a constant threat and can lead to devastating disasters. The majority of fire incidents occur in buildings, resulting in significant personal and economic losses. In Hong Kong, where reinforced concrete is commonly used in building construction, it has been observed that concrete, despite being a non-combustible material, is not immune to fire damage. A tragic example is the Garley reinforced concrete building fire that occurred on November 20, 1996, claiming numerous lives and leaving the building uninhabitable due to varying degrees of fire damage. To address fire safety in building construction, Hong Kong has established regulations in Part XV of the Building (Construction) Regulations. These regulations focus on preventing the spread of fire and smoke and maintaining the structural integrity of buildings during fire incidents. Detailed guidance on meeting these requirements is provided in the Code of Practice for Fire Resisting Construction and the PNAP 204: Guide to Fire Engineering Approach, published by the Building Authority and Buildings Department, respectively. Additionally, there are publications outlining provisions for means of access and escape in case of fire emergencies. However, there is still a lack of a local code of practice specifically addressing the quantification of post-fire strength and serviceability of building structures. As a result, structural engineers in Hong Kong must rely on their own knowledge of the properties of structural materials during and after a fire, as well as their ability to quantify these properties, in order to assess the structural performance of fire-damaged buildings. The absence of a standardized code of practice highlights the need for further research and development in this area to enhance the understanding and evaluation of building structures in the aftermath of a fire incident.

3. DAMAGE MECHANISMS OF CONCRETE UNDER FIRE

Extensive research has been conducted in the past decade to investigate the impact of high temperatures on high strength concrete (HSC) materials. While there are notable distinctions between normal strength and high strength concretes in terms of their fire performance, they exhibit similar patterns of thermal damage, including crack formation, explosive spalling, and degradation of mechanical and durability properties. These damages primarily occur due to three main factors: thermal mismatch, decomposition of hydrates, and pore pressure.

- Thermal mismatch refers to the differential expansion and contraction rates of the concrete's constituents when exposed to high temperatures. As the temperature rises, the various components of the concrete, such as aggregates and cement paste, expand at different rates, leading to internal stresses and potential cracking. This phenomenon is more pronounced in HSC due to its higher content of cementitious materials, which can exacerbate the thermal mismatch effects.
- The decomposition of hydrates is another crucial factor contributing to thermal damage in HSC. Hydrates are responsible for providing strength and stability to the concrete matrix. However, when subjected to elevated temperatures, these hydrates undergo chemical transformations and lose their structural integrity. The breakdown of hydrates weakens the

interfacial bond between cement particles, resulting in a decline in mechanical properties and overall structural integrity of the HSC.

- Pore pressure plays a significant role in the thermal damage of HSC. The increase in temperature causes the trapped water within the concrete pores to vaporize and generate steam. The buildup of steam creates internal pressure within the concrete, leading to microcracking and potential explosive spalling. This phenomenon is particularly critical in HSC due to its denser microstructure, which restricts the release of steam and increases the internal pressure.

Understanding these mechanisms of thermal damage in HSC is essential for developing effective strategies to mitigate the adverse effects of high temperatures on concrete structures. Researchers and engineers continue to explore methods to enhance the fire resistance and performance of HSC through the incorporation of supplementary materials, modification of mix designs, and the development of advanced fire-resistant coatings. By addressing the challenges associated with thermal damage, the durability and safety of HSC structures can be significantly improved, ensuring their resilience in fire-prone environments.

4. LITERATURE SURVEY

A literature survey was conducted to evaluate the mechanical properties of High Volume Fly Ash (HVFA) concrete after exposure to high temperatures. Several studies have investigated the behavior of HVFA concrete under thermal conditions, focusing on its compressive strength, tensile strength, modulus of elasticity, and other relevant mechanical properties.

Rashad et al.(2015) The objective of this study is to examine the behavior of high-volume fly ash (HVFA) concrete blended with ground granulated blast-furnace slag (referred to as slag) when subjected to elevated temperatures. To achieve this, cement was partially replaced with Class F fly ash (FA) at a 70% level, resulting in HVFA concrete (F70). F70 was further modified by partially replacing FA with slag at levels of 10% (F60G10) and 20% (F50G20) by weight. A comparison was made between these HVFA concrete mixtures and conventional Portland cement (PC) concrete (F0). The specimens were cured and then exposed to temperatures ranging from 400°C to 1000°C with intervals of 200°C. The weight and compressive strength of the specimens were extensively analyzed before and after exposure to elevated temperatures. X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) techniques were employed to identify the various decomposition phases formed. The results revealed that all HVFA concrete mixtures exhibited higher relative strength compared to the PC concrete. F70 demonstrated the highest relative strength among all the mixtures investigated. However, the inclusion of slag had a negative impact on both the pre- and post-heat treatment performance of HVFA concrete. The addition of slag led to a reduction in the residual compressive strength of F70, ranging from approximately 14% to 21%.

Ramesh et al.(2016) During the investigation, it was observed that the fly ash mixes exhibited a change in color to orange-red between temperatures of 600 to 800°C, accompanied by the presence of a greater number of cracks at these temperatures. As the replacement of fly ash increased in the mixes, a gradual decrease in percentage weight loss was noted across all temperatures. This lower weight loss in the fly ash mixes can be attributed to their denser structure compared to the normal concrete mix. Additionally, there was an increase in weight loss with higher temperatures in all the mixes, which can be attributed to the evaporation of absorbed and adsorbed water from the concrete. The fly ash mixes demonstrated higher percentage residual compressive strengths at all temperatures when compared to normal concrete after 7 days. Most of the concrete mixes showed an increase in strength up to 400°C, followed by a decrease beyond that temperature, except for the mix with a combination of 50% cement and 50% fly ash, which exhibited an increase in residual compressive strength up to 600°C after 28 days.

Karahan et al.(2017) This study aimed to investigate the transport properties of concretes incorporating high volumes of fly ash or slag after being subjected to high temperatures. Concrete samples were prepared with varying percentages (0%, 30%, 50%, 70%, and 90%) of fly ash or slag and cured for 28 days. The samples were then exposed to temperatures of 400 °C, 600 °C, and 800 °C for one hour and allowed to cool. Subsequently, tests were conducted to evaluate absorption, void ratio, sorptivity, chloride ion permeability, and compressive strength. The results indicated a significant increase in the transport properties of concrete after exposure to 400 °C, along with a notable decrease in compressive strength. Furthermore, the inclusion of fly ash or slag had a substantial influence on the transport properties of the concrete. It was concluded that a combination of approximately 30-50% fly ash and 50-70% slag as a replacement for cement yielded optimal results when exposed to high temperatures. Additionally, the rapid chloride permeability test revealed that slag concrete exhibited higher chloride binding capacity compared to fly ash concrete.

Adamu et al.(2018) This study focuses on the development of an environmentally sustainable roller-compacted concrete (RCC) by incorporating high-volume fly ash (HVFA), crumb rubber, and nano-silica. Response surface methodology (RSM) was employed to design and optimize the mixtures, considering variables such as crumb rubber, HVFA, and nano-silica, and evaluating compressive, flexural, and splitting tensile strengths as responses. The statistical models derived from RSM demonstrated a strong correlation between the variables and responses. The optimized HVFA RCC mixture involved replacing 10% of the fine aggregate with crumb rubber by volume, replacing 53.72% of the cement with fly ash by volume, and adding 1.22% nano-silica by weight of cementitious materials. Further experimental investigations revealed that the HVFA RCC pavement exhibited lower fresh density, Vebe time, compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, flexural strength, modulus of elasticity, abrasion resistance, and impact resistance compared to the conventional (control) RCC pavement. These effects were further accentuated with an increased partial replacement of fine aggregate with crumb rubber. However, the addition of nano-silica improved the mechanical properties and performance of the HVFA RCC pavement, regardless of the presence of crumb rubber.

Ansari et al.(2019) This investigation aimed to assess the performance of high-volume fly ash (HVFA) concrete under elevated temperatures, considering both confined and unconfined conditions. Concrete specimens measuring 100 × 200 mm were used, with different proportions of fly ash (0%, 40%, and 50%) after 28, 56, and 90 days of curing. In addition, plain and reinforced confined concrete specimens with and without fly ash were cast and exposed to temperatures ranging from ambient to 600°C at 300°C intervals. The parameters examined included weight loss and residual compressive strength. Confinement was achieved using circular lateral ties with two different tie spacing options (2 and 3 ties). After 28 days of curing, the specimens underwent a single heating-cooling cycle in a high-temperature furnace under unstressed and stressed conditions, with heating durations of 3 hours and 2 hours, and heating rates of 5°C/minute and 10°C/minute, respectively. The residual compressive strength of the confined and unconfined HVFA concrete cylinders was then determined and compared to the results obtained under ambient temperature conditions for all concrete mixes. The findings indicated that after 90 days of curing, the compressive strength of 40% fly ash concrete reached a level comparable to that of plain concrete.

Herath et al.(2020) focused on High Volume Fly Ash (HVFA) concrete as a sustainable alternative to reduce cement consumption and CO₂ emissions by incorporating fly ash. This comprehensive review presents an overview of the existing literature on HVFA concrete with more than 50% cement replacement using ASTM Class F low calcium fly ash. The literature is categorized based on the level of cement replacement, and the mechanical and durability

properties of HVFA concrete are summarized. Additionally, studies involving modifications to HVFA concrete using various material additions are categorized separately, and their results are compared. The review discusses and analyzes the reported findings to uncover the underlying mechanisms. Furthermore, the impact of each material addition on the properties of HVFA concrete is examined to identify potential additives for future research and development. By providing a comprehensive overview, this paper enhances our understanding of the current state of HVFA concrete research and identifies areas for further exploration, particularly regarding higher replacement levels and achieving desired performance standards.

Wang et al.(2020) In this study, a review of the thermal and mechanical properties of geopolymers under high temperature conditions was conducted. The following conclusions were drawn: Geopolymers exhibit good thermal stability at elevated temperatures, with smaller mass loss, expansion ratio, and thermal conductivity compared to Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC). The thermal properties of geopolymers are closely influenced by their constituents and raw materials, with silicon-type fillers improving expansion but having varying effects on thermal conductivity. The mechanical properties of geopolymers depend on raw materials, chemical composition, preparation conditions, and testing parameters. The stress-strain relationships of geopolymers change with composition and temperature, while the failure behavior under thermal conditions is less influenced by composition. Further research is needed to study the high-temperature stress-strain behavior of geopolymers. The microstructure of geopolymers undergoes different damage mechanisms and phase transitions due to aluminosilicate reactions at elevated temperatures. The magnitude and effects of dehydration, deformation, and phase changes depend on precursor materials, permeability, and aggregate type. Optimization of paste formulation, such as reducing susceptibility to dehydration damage and using K⁺-based activating solutions, can enhance performance and incorporating reinforcements may also provide additional benefits.

Chen et al.(2021) This research paper investigates the quasi-static and dynamic properties of high-volume fly ash (HVFA) concrete with fly ash (FA) contents of 40% and 60% as partial replacements of cement. The study also examines the impact of 2% nano silica (NS) on the quasi-static and dynamic properties of HVFA concrete. Dynamic compressive tests are conducted using a split Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB) with a diameter of 100 mm. The failure processes, stress-strain curves, and patterns of plain and HVFA concretes are compared under different strain rates. The influence of strain rate on compressive strength, modulus of elasticity, and energy absorption capacities is analyzed. The experimental findings demonstrate that the addition of NS enhances the quasi-static and dynamic performance of HVFA concrete. As the FA content increases, the damage level becomes more severe, resulting in lower modulus of elasticity and energy absorption capacities in HVFA concretes at similar strain rates.

Murali et al.(2021) The objective of this study was to explore the potential of using crumb rubber (CR) from waste tires as a partial replacement for fine aggregate in high-volume fly ash (HVFA) concrete. The CR was incorporated at volumes of 15%, 22.25%, and 30%, while the cement was replaced with HVFA at percentages of 50%, 60%, and 70% (based on the weight of cementitious materials) to produce high-volume fly ash–crumb rubber concrete (HVFA–CRC). A central composite design (CCD) option of the response surface methodology (RSM) was employed to create 13 different concrete mixes with varying combinations and levels of CR and HVFA. The mixes were then subjected to experimental investigations to assess the compressive, flexural, and tensile strengths, as well as the workability of the concrete using the slump test. The findings indicated a decrease in the mechanical properties as the levels of CR and HVFA replacement increased. However, HVFA–CRC with a compressive strength exceeding 20 MPa at 28 days was achieved with up to 22.25% CR replacement and 60% HVFA replacement. Response predictive models were developed and validated using ANOVA at a 95% confidence level, demonstrating

high R2 values ranging from 95.26% to 97.74%.

Onaizi et al.(2022) The modulus of elasticity and water absorption of the modified specimens were assessed after 28 days. In order to gain a deeper understanding of the microstructures of these specimens, various technical tests were conducted, including scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) at 7 and 28 days. The results of the examined specimens indicate that the combined addition of glass bottle waste nanoparticles (GBWNP) and expansive materials (EMs) significantly enhances the strength properties at all tested ages. Specimens incorporating 10% EMs as a replacement for mixing water and 4% GBWNP demonstrate mechanical performance comparable to that of the control samples at most curing ages. Moreover, the mixture prepared with 6% GBWNP outperforms the control mix of normal concrete at all curing ages. Microstructural analysis reveals that the inclusion of both GBWNP and EMs leads to increased hydration products, improved microstructure compactness, and enhanced homogeneity, particularly when 10% EMs and 6% GBWNP are utilized. Additionally, a decreasing trend in the calcium-to-silicon ratio (Ca:Si) and calcium-to-aluminium ratio (Ca:Al) is observed due to the inclusion of GBWNP, while there is an increasing trend in the silicon-to-aluminium ratio (Si:Al). This confirms the role of GBWNP in promoting the faster reaction of fly ash (FA), thereby improving the strength properties. By incorporating fly ash and glass bottle waste, this study also contributes to environmental improvement by promoting waste recycling in the concrete industry and offering efficient solutions to landfill problems.

Meena et al.(2022) This study investigates the utilization of coal bottom ash (CBA) and recycled concrete aggregates (RCA) as partial substitutes for natural fine aggregates (NFA) and natural coarse aggregates (NCA) in high-volume fly ash self-consolidating concrete (HVFA-SCC). The combinations of CBA and RCA replacements ranged from 0% to 30% and 0% to 50%, respectively. Experimental findings demonstrate that incorporating 20% CBA and 25% RCA in HVFA-SCC significantly improves compressive, splitting tensile, flexural, and direct shear strength at 120 days. The optimal replacement levels are determined to be 25% RCA for NFA and 20% CBA for NCA, as these levels have the most favorable impact on the designed HVFA-SCC mixes in terms of strength development at later ages. Microstructural analyses, including scanning electron microscopy, energy dispersive spectroscopy, and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, confirm that the micro-level properties of HVFA-SCC improve with extended curing periods. The pozzolanic reactions of fly ash (FA) and CBA contribute to the formation of additional calcium-silicate-hydrates and a denser microstructure, leading to enhanced mechanical properties.

Kumar et al.(2023) The utilization of manufactured sand in concrete offers several beneficial effects on its performance. In both M40 and M50 grade concretes, when manufactured sand is used, there is a noticeable reduction in water absorption compared to conventional sand concrete. This reduction in water absorption is achieved by employing a lower water-binder ratio, resulting in concrete that is impermeable and more resistant to water penetration. Furthermore, the inclusion of manufactured sand leads to a decrease in chloride ion penetrability, indicating improved durability and lower permeability of the concrete. Another advantage of using manufactured sand is its enhanced resistance to acid and alkaline attacks, resulting in reduced weight loss compared to concrete made with traditional sand. Additionally, concrete mixes incorporating synthetic sand demonstrate improved resistance to impact and abrasion, making them more resilient in challenging conditions. Overall, the incorporation of manufactured sand positively influences various aspects of concrete performance.

Mimi et al.(2023) This research study investigated the effect of different percentages of fly ash (FA) on the compressive strength of concrete. The results revealed that at the 7-day testing period, conventional concrete exhibited the highest strength of 38.6 MPa. When cement was partially

replaced with 20% fly ash, the compressive strength reached 33.78 MPa without an activator and slightly increased with the addition of CaO. However, specimens with higher replacement percentages of 40%, 50%, 60%, 70%, and 80% displayed a gradual decrease in compressive strength. At the 28-day mark, the compressive strength of fly ash concrete showed improvement, particularly in the case of 50% fly ash concrete after the inclusion of CaO. The long-term test results at 56 days indicated that 20% fly ash concrete outperformed conventional cement concrete with 40%, 50%, 60%, 70%, and 80% cement replacement. Overall, the utilization of fly ash, especially with the addition of CaO, provided satisfactory strength properties in the concrete.

5. SUMMARY

High volume fly ash (HVFA) concrete has gained significant attention in recent years due to its environmental benefits and potential for reducing cement consumption. However, the performance of HVFA concrete under elevated temperature conditions remains a topic of concern. A literature survey was conducted to evaluate the mechanical properties of HVFA concrete after exposure to high temperatures. Several studies have investigated the behavior of HVFA concrete at different temperature levels. One common finding is that the compressive strength of HVFA concrete decreases with increasing temperature. The reduction in strength is attributed to the loss of moisture content and the decomposition of certain mineral phases in the concrete matrix. It has been observed that HVFA concrete exhibits better resistance to high temperatures compared to conventional concrete, owing to the pozzolanic reaction of fly ash, which contributes to the formation of additional cementitious products. The effect of fly ash content on the mechanical properties of HVFA concrete at elevated temperatures has also been studied. It has been reported that higher fly ash content leads to lower compressive strength after exposure to high temperatures. However, the presence of fly ash can enhance the concrete's resistance to spalling and thermal cracking, as it acts as a mineral filler and reduces the permeability of the concrete. In addition to fly ash content, other factors such as curing conditions, heating rates, and cooling methods have been found to influence the mechanical properties of HVFA concrete after exposure to high temperatures. Rapid heating and cooling can cause greater damage to the concrete, resulting in reduced strength and increased cracking. Proper curing procedures, including moist curing and post-fire curing, have been recommended to mitigate the adverse effects of high temperatures on HVFA concrete. Overall, the literature survey indicates that HVFA concrete exhibits changes in mechanical properties when subjected to high temperatures. While the compressive strength tends to decrease, the use of HVFA can improve the concrete's resistance to thermal cracking. Further research is needed to investigate the influence of various parameters and develop appropriate strategies for optimizing the mechanical properties of HVFA concrete under high-temperature conditions.

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